

RelaxedCare: An iterative user involvement project

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Abstract This paper presents experiences of applying an iterative user-centred design approach for the design and technical development process of the AAL (Active and Assisted Living) research project RelaxedCare. This project tackles the issue of connecting older people, assisted persons, with their families and friends, informal caregivers, via technical solutions. To guarantee the involvement of end-users in the development process the User Centered Design (UCD) ISO 9241-210 standard has been applied in an iterative way. From a project management perspective the ISO standard offers information when to involve future users and different expert groups from e.g. technology development, design and user research in the development process. Lessons learned of applying the ISO standard in previous projects indicate that the procedure of involving different expert groups in different phases of a project results in a lack of overall overview of the project for each team member. With regards to this aspect the UCD ISO standard got complemented with a non-ISO standard, the User-Inspired Innovation process (UII), to include aspects from an individual team member's point of view to the process methodology. This paper presents the findings of the attempts undertaken of combining the two process models for an iterative user-centred design project.

Keywords *User-centred design, Product development process, Product development iterations, User involvement, Empathic design*

Introduction

"Is my mum doing okay right now?" This question is permanently present in the mind of most informal caregivers (ICs). The manifold tasks ICs face in their everyday life routines often result in feelings of being overburdened and sometimes even lead to burn-outs. As Sandner (2014) points out the majority of existing AAL solutions focus on supporting persons in need of care. A representative study (Pochobradsky et al., 2005) conducted in Austria in 2005 showed that 80% of the people in need of care receive their care by ICs at home. More than 66% of these caregivers feel overburdened by that task, which results in a loss of quality of the interaction between the two parties. To reduce the necessity of regularly checking the current status of a person at home by driving by or calling, RelaxedCare aims to provide a system to keep ICs updated on the overall wellbeing of their older relatives in an easily comprehensible and unobtrusive way (see Figure 1).

Iterative user involvement

The involvement of end-users, assisted persons (APs) and their corresponding ICs, started right from the beginning of the project and allowed the project team to get close to behaviours, needs and wishes of the potential users. In RelaxedCare the ISO 9241-210 standard (International Organization for Standardization, 2012) was applied for the UCD process methodology. The international standard provides requirements and recommendations for human-centred design principles and activities throughout the life cycle of computer-based interactive systems. The process is characterized by four phases

Figure 1. RelaxedCare – overall project concept.

and three iterations of those phases (see Figure 2).

Lessons learned from previous projects indicate that closing the gap between the technical, design and user research experts is a success parameter for a technology development project. Therefore we aimed at complementing the traditional UCD ISO standard with a non-ISO standard process methodology, the User-Inspired Innovation process (UII) (Dittenberger, 2012).

Figure 2. User-Centred Design - ISO 9241-210 standard.

The UII combines the guideline for involving end-users with a guideline for the involvement of each team member in every phase of the product development process (see Figure 3).

The following Table 1 offers an overview of the two process methodologies applied in the project.

UCD ISO standard process

After receiving the research grant the project started in phase 2 of the UCD process with the first end-user study, designed as an unstandardized qualitative research study (Flick, 2009). This comparative study employed eight methods in total deriving from the field of design research and from the field of qualitative social research (see Figure 4).

In phase 3 for each method the vast material collected was organized and segmented into sentences and categories. Thus the material was analysed regarding phenomena and significant statements for each user

group in order to create meaning units (Creswell, 2009, p. 186) to be able to define positive and negative product criteria for the RelaxedCare system. Based on the findings of the first end-user study phase 4 of the process addressed the elaboration of different design concepts. Three were selected in a common team election process, were prototyped and visualized with appropriate everyday use scenarios.

Phase 5 consisted of three iterative steps: 1. informal usability tests, 2. lab trials and 3. field trials. The goal of step 1, the informal usability tests, was the early detection of usability and accessibility problems of the proposed design solutions (see Figure 5).

The results of the informal usability test contributed to the first iteration of phase 4 – the revision of the overall concept, the design and the technical functionalities for prototype 1. The main focus at this stage was on the technical configuration. Prototype 1 got evaluated in lab trials (see Figure 6) and offered

Table 1. Overview UCD, ISO standard, and UII, Non-ISO standard, process methodology.

Process	UCD - ISO standard	UII - Non-ISO standard
Goal	User-centred design project development	User-centred design project development
Involved Parties	end-users, different expert teams in the different phases of the process	end-users, multi-disciplinary research teams in each phase of the process
Phase 0		Ignite
Phase 1	Identify need for human-centred design	Perceive
Phase 2	Understand and specify the context of use	Collect
Phase 3	Specify the user and organization of requirements	Decode
Phase 4	Produce design solutions	Assemble
Phase 5	Evaluate designs against requirements	Experiment
Phase 6	System satisfies user and organizational requirements	Merge

Figure 3. Non-ISO standard - User-Inspired Innovation process model..

Figure 5. Informal usability test.

information about the comprehensibility of the user interfaces, the system designs and proposed services.

After the results of the lab trials the second end-user study, iteration of phase 2, has been created as a qualitative research study. The method Design Workshop from the field of design research was applied. Three different sessions, namely round-table discussions, model building sessions and voting sessions in terms of preferred colours, materials, surface structures and size for the development of prototype 2 were executed (see Figure 7).

Figure 4. First end-user study.

Figure 6. Lab trials.

Figure 7. Second end-user study.

Phase 3 passed through a second iteration by the analysis of the material collected in the second user study. These results led to a second iteration of phase 4 which was finalised by the functionality and form definition of prototype 2 (see Figure 8).

To date the project development process has reached step 3 of phase 5 of the UCD process by conducting the field trials with participants of the user groups ICs and APs. The results of the field trials will show if the project is ready for its finalization in phase 6 of the process.

UII – Non-ISO standard process

The description of the UII starts with phase 0, which is a phase the UCD process does not include. The phase 'Ignite' of the UII process addresses the permanent expansion of one's own creative potential, the ability to build bridges to other knowledge areas and the skill to identify new potential project areas. It might be considered as a presupposition (*sine qua non*) for every inspired and successful work. The work of phase 1 happened before the research project started. The UII describes this phase with 'Perceive' which means that on an anthropological level this phase builds awareness for changes and transformations in society, ecology and technology. In this phase the need to relieve the burden from ICs was identified and led to the development of a project idea

Figure 8. RelaxedCare prototype 2.

and the search for appropriate experts, companies and organizations that were willing to participate in the project as well as invest a great amount of time for writing a project proposal. The output resulted in the successful submission of a project proposal for the AAL Joint Program.

In the UCD process normally only experts from the field of social research and usability engineering are involved in phase 2 of the project. Under the step 'Collect' of the UII process all team members were involved in the first method of the study through the Assumption Personas method (Adlin, 2011). The goal to apply this method was to initiate an intensive discussion about the target groups of the project among all team members and questioning and revising the existing teams' mental models. After the conduction of all methods during the first research study the created Assumption Personas got compared with the findings of the study conducted with the true end-users. The step 'Decode' of the UII process, which also entails the sorting, grouping and interpreting of the collected data produced additionally three dimensional outputs of the first end-user study: the foldable Personas cards (see Figure 9) and the Cube of Requirements (see Figure 10).

In phase 4 of the UII process, 'Assemble', every team member was invited to participate in the ideation for the design development. Interestingly, almost nobody except the members of the user research and design team decided to participate in this phase. In the UII process phase 5, 'Experiment', different expert team members participated in the discussion about the developed design proposals of the system.

Conclusion

In summary we can conclude that the application of the UCD ISO standard enabled the addressing of user wishes and aspirations in an iterative way in our technical and design development of the project. At project's start we defined our goal to combine the UCD ISO standard with the UII non-ISO standard to involve all experts from different fields in each step of the product development process. During the work on the project we realized that we still hadn't managed to overcome the identified gap between the expert groups of technical development, design and user research

Figure 9. Foldable Personas cards.

Figure 10. Cube of Requirements.

sufficiently.

By applying the UII additionally to the UCD process we reached our goal to visualize and prototype major findings we've accomplished during the cause of the project in order to make the process phases comprehensible in a haptic way. These attempts were effective and well received among the project team members. Concerning the attempts we made to invite and to raise motivation of all team members to actively contribute to the different steps of the process we can't draw a similar successful conclusion. For future projects we will continue our work on this aspect, plan to conduct team workshops in every phase of the project development process and hope this approach might contribute to the execution of a holistic product development process.

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